

Pre-Experimental Study Regarding Prevention of Home Accident Among Mothers of Under Five Year Children in Selected Rural Area, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: Children are by nature accident prone. The greatest number of accidental injuries occurs in 2-3 years and 5-year age. Most children are injured at home and older children are injured outside the home. Mothers of under five-year-old children are the best group in order to implement educational programs since they play caring and supportive roles for their children. **Objective:** To assess the knowledge on prevention of home accident among mothers of under five-year children. To find out the effectiveness of Structured teaching programme on prevention of home accident. To find out association between pre-test knowledge score with selected socio demographic variables. **Methodology:** An evaluative study approach with pre-experimental research design one group pre-test post-test design was used for the study. The study was conducted in selected rural area of Bilaspur (C.G.). The sample of the study chosen by non-probability Purposive Sampling Technique, which includes 60 mothers of under five-year children. A self-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. The collected data was analyzed on the basis of the descriptive and inferential statistics. **Result:** The result showed that post-test mean score (16.4) was significantly higher than pre-test mean score (10.78). The 't' value of the study was 15.21 at $P < 0.05$. The study revealed that the Structured teaching programme on prevention of home accidents among mothers of under five Years children was highly effective. The finding of the study also revealed that there was significant association between pre-test knowledge score with selected socio demographic variables like type of family & monthly income of family. The study finding revealed that there is no significant association between the level of knowledge with their selected demographic variables like age, education, number of children, occupation of mother, and source of previous knowledge. **Conclusion:** The study indicate that pre-test knowledge score was poor among mother of under five-year children regarding prevention of home accident and after administration of Structured teaching programme, post-test knowledge score become increased as compare to pre-test knowledge score. There is need to give interventional program to improve knowledge prevention of home accidents for positive health impact and better quality of life on children.

Keywords: Home accident, Knowledge.

1. Introduction

Children are by nature accident prone. They are curious,

investigative, impulsive, impatient and less careful to listen warning accidental injuries are the leading cause of hospitalization disability and death of children. It is expensive aspect of community health. The greatest number of accidental injuries occurs in 2-3 years and 5-year age. Most children are injured at home and older children are injured outside of home.

According to the world health report given by the department of injuries and violence prevention (2000), among the leading cause of death in both genders in the 0 yr to 4 yrs age group, falls ranks in the 12th position. The same WHO (2000) report further indicates that in the 0 yr to 4 yrs age group the leading cause of burden of disease, south east Asia region. India, ranks the 11th position.

Home accident are the main cause of mortality and morbidity in early childhood and a major factor in lost productive life. The public health experts have created the term "Modern Day Epidemic" for domestic accidents. WHO calls domestic accident as a priority Problem. An infant in fragile helpless and innocent when it enters world it is completely dependent on its caretakers. Children are especially at risk for injury because of their normal curiosity impulsiveness and desire to master new skills also children try to imitate adult behavior from an early age. It is important to know the pattern of trauma in children from developing countries as significant differences exists in socioeconomic pattern government regulatory policies in comparison with the developed nation.

Accidents were an unexpected and undesirable score of events; especially one's resulting in damage or harm. As per WHO, unintentional injuries are a leading cause of death among children under five years of age. The unintentional injuries comprise of accidents such as falls, burns, drowning, poisoning, and aspiration of foreign material. This challenges the children's morbidity and mortality.

Many household level injury risks are avoidable requiring environmental modification which can be done with minimal efforts, suited to the affordability and feasibility for the family. Measures to prevents accident at home should be targeted

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towards those at most risk parents of preschool children and the lower social class groups. So, there is a need to conduct a study on the mothers knowledge in the prevention of home accident among children. Parents should be motivated to have knowledge about the risk factors of child injuries and safety measures to be taken to prevent home accident among children.

2. Material and Methods

An evaluative study approach with one group pre-test post-test research design was used for the study. The study was conducted in selected rural area of Bilaspur (C.G.). The sample of the study chosen by Purposive Sampling Technique, which includes 60 mothers of under five-year children. A self-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data which consists of Socio demographic include age, education, types of family, no of children, occupation of mothers, monthly income of family, source of previous knowledge and 20 self-structured multiple-choice questions used to assess the knowledge regarding prevention of home accident. The subjects were classified as follows based on their score includes adequate knowledge between (15-20), moderate knowledge (8-14), inadequate knowledge (0-7). The constructed tool along with blue print and objectives of the study were validated by taking opinion from experts for content validity. Reliability of tool was tested by split half method and Reliability is $r = 0.85$. So, the tool were reliable. In order to test the feasibility and practicability pilot study was conducted in khaira village, Bilaspur (C.G.) after obtaining written permission from 10 mothers of under five-year children who met the inclusion criteria. The data was collected from Lagra village, Bilaspur (C.G.) After selecting the sample an informed consent obtained and confidentiality assured. The self-structured questionnaire regarding prevention of home accident is administered to 60 mothers of under five-year children. The pretest knowledge was assessed on day one and same day Structured teaching programme was conducted regarding prevention of home accident and on 7th day post test was conducted. The collected data was analyzed on the basis of the descriptive and inferential statistics.

3. Result

Findings related to Frequency and percentage distribution of under five-year children mothers according to socio demographic variable. Finding shows that maximum subject i.e. 31(51.67%) were age group of 20-25 year. maximum no. of subject i.e. 31(51.67%) were belongs to the middle school educational qualification. With regards to the type of family maximum no. of subjects 33 (55%) belonged to nuclear family, with regards to the no. of children maximum no. of subject i.e. 24(40%) were having 2 children, occupation of mother, maximum no. of subjects 39(65%) were housewife, monthly income of family maximum subject i.e. 41(68.33%), maximum subject i.e. 42(70%) of under five-year children mother among 60 samples belongs to the family member.

Findings related to level of knowledge in according to scoring criteria pre-test and post-test knowledge score study

finding shows in the pre- test knowledge 9(15%) had adequate knowledge, 41(68.33%) had moderate knowledge and 10(16.67%) had inadequate knowledge. After the Structured teaching programme on prevention of home accident the study result were 48(80%) had adequate knowledge, 12(20%) had moderate knowledge and 0(0%) had inadequate knowledge in the post- test.

Findings related to Assessment of pre-test and post-test knowledge score regarding prevention of home accident among under five-year children's mothers-study finding shows that pre-test the mean knowledge score was 10.78 and mean percent was (17.93%) and post- test mean knowledge score was 16.4 and mean percent was (27.35%). the SD of pre-test was 3.20 and post-test SD was 2.13, hence post test score was greater than pre test knowledge score. 't' value was 15.21 which is significant at $P < 0.05$ level of significance. It indicated that there was significant increase in knowledge level among mothers of under five-year children after Structured teaching programme on prevention of home accident.

Findings related to significant association between knowledge score and demographic variables it was founded that the finding of the study also revealed that there was significant association between knowledge score with selected socio demographic variables like type of family & monthly income of family. The study finding revealed that there is no significant association between the level of knowledge with their selected demo-graphic variables like age, education, number of children, occupation of mother, and source of previous knowledge.

4. Conclusion

There was statistically significant effectiveness seen in knowledge of mothers of under five-year children thus the Structured teaching programme on prevention of home accidents was found to be effective in improving knowledge of mothers of under five years children.

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